

The essence of processes of globalization, globalism and sustainable development

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Globalization as a new philosophical topic

In order to create a clearer picture of the present era, it is important to consider that the world history until the beginning of the 20th century consisted of civilizations that developed independently and did not seriously affect each other. Today, the world has changed significantly as a result of the active integration of all aspects of society over the last hundred years and has become a whole organism. As a result of this, serious changes began to take place in the social consciousness of some peoples and all humanity, marked by global processes and general (world-wide) problems caused by them. It became clear that the world community has entered a new stage of its development, which differs from the previous stages not only in the scale of changes, but also in the level of activity and its universal nature.

The whole set of these changes, as well as their causes, was called globalization (lat. Globus – globe) in the 1990s. Globalization is the process of universalization, the formation of structures, connections and relations that are unique to the entire planet Earth in various aspects of society's life. Also, globalization is characterized by the connectivity of the global space, a single world economy, general ecological interconnection, global communications, and so on.

Globalism. Numerous efforts to understand the newest trends in world development have led to the emergence of globalistics, an interdisciplinary field of scientific research aimed at understanding the nature, trends and causes of globalization processes, the global problems arising under their influence, and the consequences of these processes. Led to In a broader sense, the term «globalistics» refers to scientific, philosophical, cultural and practical studies of various aspects of globalization and global problems,

including their results, as well as practical activities related to their implementation on the economic, social and political fronts, both at the level of some countries and at the international level.

Globalistics as an independent scientific direction and field of social practice began to take shape in the late 1960s, but the objective grounds for its emergence were formed much earlier.

The history of the formation of global processes. The first signs of the current globalization process can be seen from the end of the 15th century, and by the beginning of the 19th century, it took a real shape. This was the period of Great geographical discoveries that ultimately led to the formation of a single geographical, to some extent economic and political world space. At the same time, geocentric approaches to understanding the world gave way to heliocentric approaches, and humanity finally managed to correctly interpret the alternation of day and night. Science, separated from philosophy, gave a strong impetus to the accumulation of knowledge and the development of technology, which led to the development of science and technology and the industrial revolution. The last mentioned events ultimately completely changed man's ability to change nature and his relationship with the environment.

By theoretically and practically proving that the earth is in the shape of a globe, humanity was the first in its history to reach the world level in the field of trade and laid the foundation for international relations on a global scale. At the same time, the first transnational trading companies were created. Soon, their activities went beyond the limits of pure trade, and they began to participate in the process of capturing and exploiting slaves, establishing plantations and settlements in the conquered territories, finally becoming the main executors of the colonial policy implemented by their countries.

Fundamental globalization is associated with the emergence of global connections, structures and relations. As a result of these processes, the world was gradually formed as a whole organism in almost all its aspects. The first signs of this type of globalization, known as fundamental, appeared in the second half of the 19th century, and by the middle of the 20th century it became a full-fledged existence.

At the same time, the economic transformation of the world was completed, and as a result of this, acute international problems of a completely new nature arose, arising from the growing interdependence of different

countries and peoples. These processes covered not only the economy, politics and social life, but also communication and communication tools, as well as the spiritual aspect – culture, science and philosophy. Various international organizations, forums, meetings, and congresses began to emerge, which was enabled by the active development of communication and mass communication tools at that time.

The end of the First World War in 1918 caused a new balance of power in the international arena and had consequences that tied the post-war relations, interests and conflicts of various countries into a tighter knot, thus making the whole world in all major indicators. Turned into a world community. After all, the globalization processes became more prominent in the period between the First and Second World Wars. In this period, the main signs of globalization:

- a) the increase of anthropogenic influence on the biosphere and the transformation of man into a real «geological force»;
- b) the active development of mass culture, first of all, in the field of cinema, music, literature, and the production of consumer goods;
- c) the invention of television, and over time it became the main promoter of mass culture and a symbol of globalization;
- g) for the first time, space and time were «reduced» to the parameters of human daily life, and it was manifested in intercontinental flights without landing.

But the unresolved conflicts and increasing interdependence led to the outbreak of World War II, the largest and longest war in human history. This time, three-quarters of the Earth's population participated in the world war, several times more victims than in the First World War.

From the point of view of the globalization of world-scale processes, both of these wars were actually different stages of the same global war. The difference between them is visible only in quantitative indicators. In essence, both wars were aimed at solving the same problems – the repartition of the world, which was divided at the beginning of the 20th century, as a whole and interconnected. The methods of waging war were also almost the same, the difference is that the level and scale of technical equipment is several times higher than in the Second World War, and the ideological influence was either radio, telephone, which did not exist in the previous war, or aviation, sea, and iron were not yet well developed. Road,

automobile transport was manifested in multiple strengthening with wide use of means of communication.

The Second World War, like the previous world war, had a series of far-reaching consequences that became a characteristic feature of the post-war world order. Among them, the most important was that the war stimulated research and practical work on the creation of a completely new type of weapon (atomic and reactive weapons). During this period, their first prototypes were tested in combat and created unlimited opportunities for humanity to turn the entire world into a wasteland and exterminate all living creatures. These same achievements of science and technology development determined the essence and content of the arms race that later escalated during the «cold war» and demonstrated in practice the delicacy of our planet and its spatial connectivity.

Another consequence of the Second World War occurred in the socio-political sphere of society, and it was manifested in the unprecedented growth of various international organizations. Among them, the United Nations (UN) stands out, without a doubt. Integration processes in Europe are also related to the end of the war, and 1946, when British Prime Minister U. Churchill called for the creation of the United States of Europe, can be considered the beginning of them.

The Nuremberg trials of the main war criminals and the main organizations of the Nazis were another important event and at the same time the first experience of global cooperation in the field of legal regulation of international relations. This process was carried out by the first International Military Tribunal in history, established by the victorious countries – USSR, USA, Great Britain and France on August 8, 1945, and was an important step towards the establishment of the current international judicial system. At the same time, the ideas of liberalism and democracy began to spread worldwide, a set of serious studies and theoretical works aimed at re-understanding the foundations of social existence, the moral foundations of society and the main principles of social development appeared.

The brilliance of globalization. The awareness of global threats and processes of globalization by the broad layers of the population, as well as the attitude towards the world community and the values corresponding to it, the formation of culture and lifestyle are characteristic features of the stage of globalization prosperity. Since the 1970s, globalization has

reached a new stage of its development and has taken on a vibrant tone. At the same time, the development of the information technology revolution accelerated, along with myth, religion, philosophy, science, and ecology, global consciousness emerged as another form of social consciousness.

The wave of globalization has significantly changed the world market, the world economy has shown its own characteristics, and created an opportunity for it to become stronger and more important than national economies. The following are important features of the globalization trend:

- a) the emergence of the «resonance effect», in which economic booms or crises pass from one country to other countries and regions that are closely related to it;
- b) creation of world markets of various goods and services;
- c) the formation of world prices for the specified goods and services, which determine the policy of the national producers of these goods and services in many ways.

Along with the internationalization of the economy and the unification of the role of money, the formation of mass society and mass culture corresponding to it has become a characteristic feature of rapid globalization and to a certain extent its legitimate product.

Thanks to modern means of transportation and communication, the factors of space and time have practically ceased to be important in the conditions of globalization. The objective need for a common language has always existed, but the volumes of world trade and capital transfer have increased many times, political relations have expanded to a global level, international public organizations, sports competitions, the tourist industry and it has become especially strong in the era of rapid globalization that has brought about such things. Today, English has become the language of intercultural communication due to a number of objective reasons.

After the emergence of the Internet in 1991, the world became increasingly connected in terms of information. The computer revolution and the development of the Internet created a new information space where everything exists but borders.

Since global problems are not only related to the whole world, but are manifested at the level of its regions and even some countries, in scientific literature, in addition to recognizing their universal importance, some of

them have a special essence and a narrower scope of influence. Differentiation from local, regional problems is also made. When studying problems at different levels as specific expressions of the philosophical categories of «generality», «particularity» and «singularity», they usually interpret them in such a way that private problems are some problems, local and regional problems are private problems, and global problems are general problems. As problems. The main criterion underlying the differentiation of the mentioned problems determines the same approach. It is called geographical because it reflects the factor of space or, in other words, the area where certain problems exist.

Private problems are problems related to a certain aspect of the state's activities, certain population centers or small natural objects. These are, as a rule, various problems arising as a result of various accidents, malfunctions, local social conflicts, etc.

The concept of local problems is applied to higher-level problems, more precisely, to problems related to certain countries or large areas of large countries. This usually refers to strong earthquakes, large floods or, for example, a civil war in a small country.

The concept of national problems sometimes reflects certain difficulties and concerns of a particular state or national community in socio-political and scientific treatment. Depending on the scale, they can be interpreted as regional or local problems.

Regional problems cover the range of important issues that arise in certain continents, large socio-economic areas of the world or much larger countries. An example of such problems can be the Chernobyl tragedy, which led to radioactive poisoning of several Eastern European countries, or the climate changes that occurred in much larger areas covering a number of countries. For example, the drought that occurred in the Sahel region in 1968 was called the «catastrophe of the century». It covered 18 countries of the African continent, in which more than 250 thousand people died as a result of famine, about 18 million head of cattle died, epidemics of dangerous diseases occurred, and the territory of this vast region was almost full of desert.

Global problems are explained by the fact that they cover the entire globe, not only the part of it directly inhabited by people, but also the rest of the Earth's surface, underground spaces, atmosphere, hydrosphere, and even outer space within the scope of human activity.

Among the various approaches to the classification of global problems today, according to the most widely recognized classification, all global problems are divided into three large groups depending on the level of tension and importance of their solution, as well as what causal connections exist between them in real life.

The uniqueness and novelty of the situation is that if any specific problems can be studied within the framework of some science or a set of several sciences, then man, society and nature can be studied in the context of their numerous interactions and interactions. Some sciences are not capable of researching global problems consisting of a complex system that covers in its dependencies. Because the scope of certain sciences is narrow to interpret the object of their research – this or that particular problem in the context of other global problems. For this reason, regardless of the specific tasks that this or that science solves, a philosophical approach to the processes and events related to them, that is, to the entire situation, including the results obtained in the end, is always a necessary condition of research.

Any certain sciences at a certain stage need a philosophical understanding of the subject of their research to one degree or another. Without such a broad approach to a specific subject of science and the problems facing humanity, neither fundamental discoveries nor the development of science in general is possible.

Thus, in this case, on the one hand, there is a question about the philosophical solution of problems, and on the other hand, about the fact that philosophy encourages the interaction of a wide range of sciences, in which their interdisciplinary integration plays an important role. Is conducted.

Although there is an opinion that philosophy studies extremely general issues that are far removed from the daily life and practice of people, it (philosophy) plays an important role in solving global problems. After all, it is well known that general theories can sometimes be more effective than most specific areas of knowledge.

While describing the specific features of the philosophical understanding of global problems, we note the features that arise from the main functions of philosophy and are unique to this form of knowledge.

First, philosophy, while forming a worldview, gives certain goals that determine the direction of human activity in many ways. In this way, philosophy fulfills its worldview formation and axiological functions.

Secondly, the lack of a comprehensive understanding of the complex systems studied within different disciplines is a serious obstacle to the mutual cooperation of these disciplines. In this sense, the methodological function of philosophy, which summarizes the theories that arise within the scope of this science, is especially important, because it helps the integration of scientific knowledge.

Thirdly, philosophy makes it possible to explain social events and processes in a historical context. It describes the general laws of the development of society and nature, and therefore, in the study of global problems, it leads to understanding them as a legal phenomenon that is inextricably linked with social development. Therefore, the emergence of global problems is not considered as a coincidence or a judgment of fate that predestined humanity to destruction, but as a product of the objective development process of human history full of contradictions.

Fourthly, philosophy makes it possible to understand the general trend of the development of global problems, their interrelationship and the level of mutual need from a philosophical point of view.

Fifth, philosophy performs a spiritual-cultural function by creating an opportunity for the development of a culture of theoretical thinking. Studying the history of philosophy of different peoples allows you to get acquainted with their culture. It is impossible to solve any of the problems facing certain peoples without connecting them to their culture.

Sixth, the ability to get a more precise target in the rapidly growing flow of scientific information on global problems is a product of a dialectical approach to the holistic view of the natural-historical process and its interpretation.

Seventh, philosophy puts the issues of the meaning of human life, death and eternity on the agenda, which is especially important in the conditions of global problems threatening humanity.

Finally, another important methodological function of philosophy is that it is directly related to the current important problems of humanity and plays a huge role in understanding and realizing the objective trends of human

development: «nature», «society», «civilization». «, «social development», «science and technology revolution» develops other categories.

Having formed a certain idea about the philosophical approach to the study of global problems of the present time, now we will consider the problems themselves, which are increasing in importance due to the strengthening of globalization processes, from this point of view.

The concept of «contemporary global problems» became widespread in the late 1960s and early 1970s, and since then has taken a firm place in the scientific and political discourse (lexicon) and public consciousness. In most cases, it is used as a term applied to global events and events. Such a situation can be encountered when events of national and universal importance are equated, for example, referring to the social problems of a particular country and calling them «global».

In philosophy, appropriate criteria for solving this task are defined, according to which this or that problem is defined as global and thus differs from a large number of other problems that do not have such a characteristic.

Etymologically, the term «global», like the term «globalization», is related to the earth. It is for this reason that it is customary to call the problems that concern the interests of all humanity, as well as the problems that belong to each person in different parts of the world, that is, they acquire a universal character, as «global». They significantly affect the development of some countries and regions as an important objective factor of world economic and social development. Solving them requires the joint efforts of most countries and organizations at the international level. At the same time, failure to solve global problems can have disastrous consequences for the future of all mankind.

The importance of global debt forecasting. The global problems of the present time are a unique, active and open system that constantly changes its state in time, because new problems of universal importance can enter it, and previous problems can disappear depending on their solution. A. Pechchei, the founder and first president of the Club of Rome, drew attention to this situation, saying that most of the problems facing humanity «are tightly intertwined, a huge sprut clawed newness is gripping the entire planet... the number of unsolved problems is growing, they are becoming more complex, their entanglement is getting more complicated, and their «clamp» is squeezing our planet more and more tightly in its grip», wrote 1.

However, no matter how complicated the knot of global conflicts is, it should be understood theoretically in order to solve it with the help of science and philosophy, that is, to distinguish the cause from the effect, the important details from the secondary details, the objective from the subjective. Given the limited human capacity and resources to influence global processes, it is important to distinguish between which problems require immediate solutions and which are of secondary importance.

In Western countries, social forecasting has emerged as a type of scientific prediction under the name «futurology» (lat. Futurum – future and Greek. Logos – teaching). This term was first used by Professor O. Flextheim of the Otto Zur Institute at West Berlin University. It should be noted that the term «futurology» is not universally recognized. For example, most of the French specialists in prediction problems believe that futurology is the basis for crude speculation about the human ability to predict the future with confidence. Instead of futurology, the term «futuristic» was proposed, which means «probable future». It emphasizes the conditionality and multiplicity of the future.

In the current period, researches related to social predictions are called «prognostics». Prognostics studies the laws, principles and methods of forecasting, develops logic problems and classifications of various types of prognostic research. It is still in its infancy, but it is already an important tool for creating scientific alternatives for the future. K. Tulenova deals with forecasting in Uzbekistan.

Pessimistic scientists predict that the Day of Judgment is near, while optimists predict that this is just a change of astronomical cycles. What awaits humanity in the near future. A person should answer this question according to the goals and results of his activity.

Daily prediction is based on the daily life experience of a person, direct observation of the frequent repetition of one or another events in nature and society. Popular weather signs can be an example of daily predictions. For example, if the sunset is caught longer than usual, you should wait for rain; if there is fog in the morning in the summer, it means that the weather will be clear during the day; The wind blows from the EAST, and the rains will soon end.

Astrological predictions are based on observation of the movement of celestial bodies, cycles of lunar and solar eclipses. Although astrological prediction was widespread in the Middle Ages, the attitude towards it

changed later. However, the development of esoteric knowledge in the 20th century recognizes the validity of astrological predictions.

Intuitive prediction is direct access to reality without scientific experience and logical observation. This type of prediction is not well studied and often underestimated. However, mind-boggling facts are known. For example, the French physician Michel Nostradamus, who lived four hundred years ago, had an unprecedented ability to predict. In his famous «Centuries» and other works, he describes not only the technical discoveries of the 20th century – submarines, airplanes, hydrogen bombs, but also the French and Russian revolutions, as well as the emergence of figures such as de Gaulle, Franco, Lenin, Stalin, Hitler, Mussolini. Also predicted that.

The history of the formation of corruption. The problem of corruption and the fight against it is one of the most urgent tasks of the present time. Because the widespread spread of this disease leads to very negative consequences. Corruption, in particular, hinders the implementation of democratic processes, slows down economic development, lowers the quality of personnel and, as a result, causes stagnation in all sectors, rooting of organized crime, loss of trust in the government, and socio-political instability.

That is why every country has been fighting against bribery in its own way, and in some countries corruption has been almost eradicated, while in other countries this evil continues to «flourish».

Reforms in Singapore can be cited as an example of a successful fight against corruption. This country has turned from a backward country of Asia into one of the most developed countries in the world in a short period of time. At the heart of this is the fight against corruption.

The government has developed a special program in this regard, according to which the activities of officials at all levels are fully transparent. Systematic control was established in the relations of officials at all levels with citizens, and the mechanism of these relations was improved in order to remove various bureaucratic obstacles.

In addition, the salaries of all officials have been significantly increased, the independence of the judicial system has been ensured, and the punishment for taking and giving bribes has been tightened. At the same time, an independent mass media was formed to inform the public about any form of corruption.

The famous saying of the leader of Singapore, Lee Kuan Yew, that a person who wants to win over corruption should be ready to arrest his relatives and close friends, shows that the fight against corruption in the country has been ruthless.

On July 7, 2008, Uzbekistan joined the UN Convention on Combating Corruption, and the Istanbul Anti-Corruption Plan (September 10, 2003) adopted within the framework of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development in March 2010. Also, the Agreement on the Eurasian Group to Combat Money Laundering and Terrorist Financing (Moscow, June 16, 2011) was ratified by the Oliy Majlis on December 13, 2011.

Today, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev: «In our society, it is necessary to fight against corruption, committing various crimes and other violations, to prevent them, and to ensure the requirements of the law that punishment for crime is inevitable. «We need to take strict measures» and stressed that «We consider it our first priority to establish the sense of justice, which our people value and value above all else, in our lives.» . For this purpose, on the initiative of the head of our country, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On Combating Corruption» was developed.

The Law «On Combating Corruption» was adopted by the Legislative Chamber on November 24, 2016, by the Senate on November 24, 2016

It was approved on December 13, signed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 3, 2017 and announced in the press on January 4, 2017. It consists of 6 chapters and 34 articles.

Article 3 of this law defines corruption as follows:

Corruption is illegal use of one's position or service position by a person for the purpose of obtaining material or immaterial benefits for personal interests or the interests of other persons, as well as illegal presentation of such benefits.

Article 4 contains the main principles of fighting against corruption. They consist of:

Legality;

Priority of rights, freedoms and legal interests of citizens;

Openness and transparency;

Systematicity;

Cooperation between the state and civil society;

Priority of measures to prevent corruption;

The inevitability of liability.

Article 5 defines the following main directions of state policy in the field of combating corruption:

Raising the legal consciousness and legal culture of the population, forming an intolerant attitude towards corruption in the society;

Implementation of measures to prevent corruption in all spheres of state and public life;

Timely identification of corruption-related offenses, putting an end to them, eliminating their consequences, reasons and conditions that enable them, ensuring the principle of inevitability of responsibility for committing corruption-related offenses.

Pursuant to Article 7 of the Law «On Combating Corruption», the state bodies that directly carry out anti-corruption activities are as follows:

General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

National Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

The Department of Combating Tax, Currency-related Crimes and Legalization of Criminal Proceeds under the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Also, citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations and other organizations, mass media and citizens participate in the fight against corruption.

The Republican Interdepartmental Commission on Combating Corruption was established to coordinate the activities of the bodies and organizations involved in the fight against corruption. In accordance with Article 8 of this

law, the formation of the Inter-Departmental Commission and the order of its activity shall be determined by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Our legislation prescribes a fine of 50 to 100 times the minimum monthly salary or imprisonment for up to 5 years with the deprivation of certain rights for taking a bribe. When this crime is committed in aggravating circumstances

A sentence of imprisonment from 10 to 15 years is imposed.

Basharti, if extortion for a bribe was made against a person, or if this person voluntarily reported about it after committing criminal acts, sincerely repented and actively helped in solving the crime, he is exempted from liability. Will be released.

The crime of bribery is punishable by a fine of up to 50 times the minimum monthly salary to imprisonment for 5 to 10 years.

For mediating bribery, a fine of up to 50 times the minimum monthly salary to imprisonment for 5 to 8 years has been established. If the person who acted as a mediator, after committing a criminal act, voluntarily reports about it, sincerely repents and actively helps in solving the crime, he will be released from responsibility.

Adoption of legislation alone is not enough to fight corruption effectively. For this, civil society should actively participate in this work, cooperation between law enforcement agencies and civil society should be strengthened, courts should be independent and impartial, laws should be based on the interests of the country, not members of parliament. To be accepted, to ensure transparency in all state bodies, active participation of mass media, to eliminate administrative and bureaucratic obstacles, to provide services through an electronic system as much as possible, to create a healthy competitive environment.

In the 20th century, under the influence of mind-boggling results in the field of science and technology, the first technocratic social theories appeared. The author of one of them, the American economist and sociologist T. Veblen, was the first to philosophically justify the leading role of industrial production and technical development in the development of society. In his opinion, the modern state should be managed by engineers and technicians, because the development of production in the interests of society (this idea is the core of T. Veblen's technocratic theory) can only be

done by them, and the political power gives them the same goal. Needed for production.

The speech was translated into many languages of the world and spread widely around the world. Then the next series of lectures appeared (today there are more than twenty of them). These lectures shed light on many aspects of universal problems and attracted the attention of not only scientists and philosophers, but also politicians, public figures, and the world community as a whole.

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